

D4.2

Annotated List of the Various Actors Involved in Modern Islamic Knowledge Production **Jens Heibach**

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Annotated List of the Various Actors Involved in Modern Islamic Knowledge Production

This deliverable revolves around religious authority and knowledge production in the European context. It aims to pinpoint an annotated list of various actors involved in modern Islamic knowledge production in the target setting.

Here, it is important to highlight that ‘religious authority’ and ‘religious knowledge production’ are conceptualized in their broader sense, and taken to be highly varying processes depending on the context. Furthermore, it should be noted that the term ‘actors’ refers to the social scientific notion of ‘acting agency’ rather than to concrete persons or institutions per se.

In this piece, we bring together three sections written by three different authors. The **first section** draws from the works of **Hayat Douhan**, who researches on Muslim diasporas in Europe. The **second section** is the work of **Aleeha Zahra Ali**, whose project explores digitization of a Shia ritual. The **final section** is by **Justin Mauro Benavidez**, who chronicles historical genealogies of knowledge between Muslim intellectuals.

The first two sections look at contemporary knowledge production in the Islamic world, and the the third section complements the discussion of the contemporary by demonstrating a historical grounding in the transmission of knowledge. In all three sections, the authors discuss Muslim intellectuals, scholars, and public figures.

Therefore all have created an emphasis on people, interpersonal relationships, and public knowledge as important in what is considered ‘Religious knowledge’. At the same time this notion is problematized by the different categories and approaches in each section, which demonstrate the multifaceted dimensions of this topic.

The sections demonstrate the evolution of the three research projects of each author, and the varying insights their work brings to the question of knowledge production in Islam.

Section 1

Knowledge Production & Dissemination among Muslim diaspora in Europe

For the purpose of this research, Islamic authority is conceptualized as any entity that a group of Muslims consult, either formally or informally, on religious matters. This could be an institution, a person, a school, or even a website. Similarly, religious knowledge production encompasses any kind of content that is produced and communicated on religious grounds regardless of its nature (form, source, etc.). I have been exploring the Muslim religious field in Europe with the aim of grasping the nature of religious authority and knowledge among Muslims with a focus on the Sunni tradition.

In this deliverable, I have tried to identify the major religious authorities, actors and/or centers of Islamic knowledge among the Muslim diasporic community in the European context. In more practical terms, I have tried to pinpoint the major formal religious institutions that are expected to produce religious knowledge in this target settings. I also asked some Muslims about the religious references they consult when faced with religious queries.

During the initial phase of my research, I have found that the Muslim religious field in Europe is characterized by three increasing and interrelated features: a) fragmentation of religious authority, b) individualization and contestation, and c) digitization of religious knowledge production. First, while the overall Muslim religious field seems to be ethnically organized forming sub-religious fields (Turkish religious field, Moroccan religious field, etc.), each sub-field is further fragmented by other factors, for instance the extent to which these Muslim associations are backed up by other bigger transnational organizations.

It has been observed that, although some Muslims still prefer the traditional way of acquiring religious knowledge by learning from the imam at the mosque, others tend to rely on themselves, making use of digital media to access religious knowledge.

This has encouraged various religious entities to construct their religious authority online; while many of them have created their social media platforms

few years ago, they all seem to invest more efforts recently to enhance their online presence. These changes have shaped the ways in which Islamic knowledge is constructed, produced and disseminated especially in the last few years.

Drawing on my online ethnographic research, I have listed a set of religious authorities, actors and/or centers of Islamic knowledge, which can be categorized into three groups: Institutional, modern, and traditional actors.

Section 1

Knowledge Production & Dissemination among Muslim diaspora in Europe

1. Institutional Actors

Although they vary in their structures, target audiences and underlying objectives/agendas, these institutional actors are official institutions that expected to act like religious authorities and/or centers of religious knowledge that would serve the Muslim diasporic 'community' in Europe. While some of these institutions are official and ethnically oriented as they are founded and backed up by state bodies (e.g. Turkey, Morocco), others are mainly founded and run by a body of religious experts from different parts of the world. These usually rely on the members' efforts to produce and disseminate religious knowledge and, therefore, construct their religious authority. It is important to note that although these actors mainly operate offline, they have all adopted new and digital media to construct and enhance their online religious authority by increasing their visibility and reaching out to a larger audience.

→**DITIB**¹: is considered to be the largest Turkish religious organization that is recognized by the Muslim Turkish diasporic community in Germany. It is governed by Directorate of Religious Affairs or Diyanet², which is a Turkish official religious state institution whose authority goes beyond the Turkish territory to have a considerable impact on the Turkish Muslims' religious fields across Europe. Although DITIB encompasses the majority of Turkish Muslim associations, there are other religious movements and/or organizations that are active in the diasporic context such as, for instance, Millî Görüş³.

→**The European Council for Moroccan Oulema (CEOM)**⁴: is an official Moroccan religious council based in Brussels, Belgium. It was founded by the Moroccan State to serve the Moroccan diasporic community in Europe.

1 <https://www.ditib.de/index.php>

2 <https://www.diyamet.gov.tr/en-US/>

3 <https://www.igmg.org>

4 <https://ceomeurope.eu>

→**The European Council for Fatwa and Research (ECFR)**⁵: is a transnational religious organization that is based in Dublin, Ireland. It encompasses a set of religious authorities based inside and outside Europe.

→**The European Council of Imams (ECI)**⁶: a European religious organization that consists of religious leaders/imams across Europe with the aim of tackling issues related to imams & Muslim associations.

2. New Actors

Based on my online participant observation, I realized that young Muslims in Europe vary in the ways they perceive religious authorities and acquire religious knowledge. Some refuse the idea of following most if not all established religious authorities; they rather prefer to rely on themselves to construct their religious knowledge and conduct research on their own. By browsing, comparing and contrasting different views, they can find satisfying answers to their questions. By contrast, others tend to acquire their Islamic knowledge by selecting specific religious authorities whom they trust and then follow their seminars and sermons on various topics. Similarly, some interviewees mentioned that when they have specific religious queries, they tend to consult particular religious councils and websites they perceive as authoritative and reliable. Accordingly, I argue that these online authorities (persons and platforms) can be considered as religious authorities and/or centers of religious knowledge production and dissemination given their popularity among a group of young Muslims in the West.

5 <https://www.e-cfr.org/>

6 <https://euimams.org/>

Section 1

Knowledge Production & Dissemination among Muslim diaspora in Europe

2.1. Religious Figures

These are examples of religious figures that some of the young Muslims tend to watch/listen to. Although they might diverge in their underlying approach and focus, they all converge in a set of interrelated points: First, they are all distinguished and controversial imams or preachers who have received modern Western education in addition to their religious knowledge; second, they have been involved in modern Islamic knowledge production tackling various topics; and third, they have invested in enhancing their online presence and/or authority and, therefore, are capable of reaching out to a large public, mainly the youth.

Name	Nationality/location	Online Presence
Adnane Ibrahim:	Palestinian-Austrian (Austria)	Website: http://www.adnanibrahim.net Youtube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCMkgz4L22HV3e-1yy9zIYPg (685K followers) Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/Dr.Ibrahimadnan/ (>600K followers) Twitter: https://twitter.com/dradnanibrahim (> 400K followers) Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/adnanibrahim_official/ (21.8 followers)
Nabil Al Awadhy:	Kuwaiti	Youtube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCpPZKwayH_pWPF20LsOhgVw (> 1M followers) Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/NabilAwadhy (Almost 2M followers) Twitter: https://twitter.com/NabilAlawadhy (> 11 M followers) Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/nabilalawadhy/ (2.6 M followers) Snapchat: https://www.snapchat.com/add/nabilalawadhy
Yusuf Estes:	American (USA)	Website: https://yusufestes.com/ Other related links: https://shareislam.com/ https://www.islamnewsroom.com/ TV: http://guideus.tv/live/ (Internet and satellite TV channel) Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/y.estes

2.2. Academics & Intellectuals

Some young Muslims stated that they prefer to acquire their Islamic knowledge from intellectuals and/or academics who may not necessarily have a religious training, but have studied and written extensively about Islam. In view of the examples provided by the interviewees, although the two thinkers listed below vary in their status and share in modern Islamic production, they seem to converge in their critical approach to Islamic thought and discourse. While they call for a paradigm shift in the readings of Islamic sources, they advocate modernist and secular values.

Name	Nationality	Example of publications/ online presence
Mohammed Arkoun	Algerian Thinker (1928-2010)	Arkoun doesn't seem to have any official online platforms, but he is a very distinguished thinker who has written on Islam in different languages (English, Dutch and Indonesian), but the majority of his publications are in French and Arabic.
Mohammed Shahrour	Syrian Thinker (1938-2019)	Website: http://shahrour.org YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/user/ShahrourVideo (124K followers) Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/Dr.Mohammad.Shahrour (276K followers) Twitter: https://twitter.com/Dr_Mhd_Shahrour (57.2K followers)

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2.3. Online Religious Websites

These are just some examples of Islamic websites that are known for their Islamic knowledge production and dissemination, but the first three seem to be the most popular among the Muslim youth (based on some of my recent online discussions).

- Islamweb.net: <https://www.islamweb.net/en/>
- Islam Question & Answer: <https://islamqa.info/en>
- Islam online: <https://islamonline.net>
- Islamway: <https://ar.islamway.net>
- Fatwa Online: <https://www.fatwa-online.com/>
- Islam Story: <https://islamstory.com>
- Dorar: <https://www.dorar.net>
- Islam News Room: <https://www.islamnewsroom.com>

3. Traditional Actors

In the course of my interviews with informants involved in the management of some Moroccan mosques/Muslim associations, I have realized that mosques as 'traditional' religious spaces still play a significant role in producing and disseminating Islamic knowledge in the Western context. There is no doubt that there is a considerable portion of the Muslim population that relies mainly on the local mosques to construct their knowledge about Islam and how to be a good Muslim.

I was told that the mosque receives queries on various topics on a regular basis. For most of the mosques, these queries are directed to the local imam, the face of religious authority in this setting, who answers them. In case the question is new or complicated, the imam would conduct further research and/or consult his or the mosque's religious network. Given the place of Muslim associations and mosques in this process, I argue that local imams and the mosques'

religious network are key actors in modern Islamic knowledge production and dissemination, especially in the diasporic European context where Islamic authority is highly fragmented.

3.1. The Local Imam

In the course of my online ethnographic research, I have interviewed a Moroccan imam/PhD researcher who has been actively involved in the Muslim field in Germany. Inquiring about the impact of digital media on the status and agency of the imam, he confirmed that digital media has been influential in making all kinds of religious knowledge accessible to the public. Therefore, Muslims, especially youth who are media literate, can find whatever information they need by themselves. In his view, this would not challenge the role of the imam as a religious guide, but it would rather increase its significance. Based on his experience, he said that sometimes young Muslims would contact him on certain matters after they had already conducted their own research online.

According to him, although the internet and new media could be a great source of religious knowledge, including unauthentic one, it could also be a source of confusion, especially when people come across a huge amount of conflictual and misleading information on the same issue. This makes some young Muslims resort to a trustful religious figure to discuss the outcome of their research and clear their confusion. This is where the imam's overall profile comes into play. He stressed that there are different types of imams and not all of them are in a good position to play this role given various factors such as the level of religious knowledge, character, involvement with the community, awareness of their context, etc. All this considered, the imam is still an active actor in the process of religious knowledge production and dissemination in its broad and informal sense. The imam may not have produced a book, but he can still be perceived as a trustful religious figure whom the community resorts to.

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3.2. The Mosque Transnational Religious Network

In addition to the imam, a mosque's religious network is another key actor in the process of knowledge production and dissemination. The significance and quality of this network depends mainly on the mosque management team as well as the association's members. According to one of my informants, over the years, the mosque has organized various conferences and workshops during which they have hosted religious experts from all over the world.

However, most of them are from Morocco for several reasons. There is a tendency to perceive the 'Moroccan' overall approach to Islam as moderate, the majority of the mosque community are Moroccan and of course, the local imam is usually Moroccan and, therefore, trained under the supervision of Moroccan ulama.

Having raised the example of the Covid-19 pandemic situation that must have posed new challenges and raised new questions, the interviewee reported that, at some point, the mosque had to decide whether or not to resume its activities in the light of the pandemic situation updates. In this situation, the mosque consulted its network of religious experts before making its own independent decision. It should be noted that the local mosque network tends to vary from one mosque to another depending on its overall profile and approach.

Section 2

Knowledge Production in a Shia *majlis*

Within the context of my research, concepts of 'religious authority' and 'knowledge production' seem at once intuitive and elusive. My work centers around the *majlis*, a religious ritual and sermon in Shi'ism. On the surface, it may seem like locating authority in a sermon is fairly straightforward. There is an *aalim* or *zaakir*⁷ seated on a raised *minbar*⁸, and the majority of the *majlis* proceeds with them addressing an intent audience.

Therefore, the reciter of a *majlis* could be an 'authority', with this status lent to them through their role in the *majlis*. This role is of a speaker commanding attention, an elicitor and mediator of emotions, and a conveyer of religious information. The contents of their speech could be 'knowledge', as indeed a *majlis* sermon communicates religious stories, beliefs, and values. This is merely the tip of the iceberg, however, and this perspective that becomes even more complicated when digitization is thrown into the mix, creating ripples both wide and deep as the spatiality and temporality of the *majlis* undulates in response.

This report considers concepts such as power, legitimacy, authenticity, knowledge (and its gate-keeping) to contribute to the constantly evolving process of authority-making. Authority is considered linked to knowledge production to include that processes of power, political motives, social networks, availability of resources, and access are all important in religious knowledge.

In this section I will consider the *majlis* in Shi'ism as a site for "production" of religious knowledge. By production here I consider a process occurring through the co-engagement of a speaker and audience, where knowledge or knowing occurs in forms beyond the textual, beyond the conveyance of information and simply verbal communication: knowledge also occurs in the body, through sensational experiences aroused not just by the words in a speech but the affective performance of oration that lend power to a ritual, communicative experience.

⁷ The words italicized in this section are from Urdu and Arabic. Aalim= scholar, zaakir= a religious speaker without formal training/education (plural: zaakireen)

⁸ Pulpit

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Knowledge and knowing also occurs through the sense of collectivity, assurance, and verification that comes from participating in a shared ritual experience. Once more, digitization adds another layer to this already intricate process.

Therefore, the actors listed in this section will be along categories pertinent to the *majlis* and its digital life: the people who read and facilitate a *majlis*; groups that organize *majalis*⁹; digital *majalis* and actors involved. The first three categories include people that also participate in *majalis* as audience members at different times, blurring the boundary between a ‘producer’ and ‘receiver’ of religious knowledge. The fourth category relating to digitization goes beyond people as actors and agents of knowledge production, and opens itself to the material dimension of knowledge beyond embodied knowledge.

This report draws from ethnographic fieldwork both online and offline amongst Dutch Shia people. However, the actors listed are active internationally, engaging with Shia communities transnationally. This endeavor, and general cross-community ties in Shi’ism, have been greatly facilitated by digitization. Dutch Shia people of various origins (Pakistani, Iraqi, Iranian, Afghan) engage with diverse sources of religious knowledge, at both the level of their physically-located communities and online.

1. Ulema/scholars

This corresponds to the categories of ‘Institutional Actors’ and ‘Academics and Intellectuals’ from Section 1 of this text¹⁰. *Ulema* and scholars¹¹ are people with some form of religious training and education, and usually some institutional affiliations with religious organizations. *Ulema* and scholars produce writings, particularly within the context of their studies. Many of them have written books and essays. However, they disseminate knowledge outside scholarly circles through debates, public talks, and speeches. Amongst the latter, the *majlis* sermons are the most popular and widely-heard. In this list, I include where these scholars have been trained to show the textual and technical basis behind their knowledge, and also the transnational dimensions of knowledge and clerical networks. All of the figures listed below recite *majalis*.

Aalim/ Scholar / Orator	Country of Origin/ Residence	Formal Religious Training
Syed Ali Raza Rizvi	Pakistan, United Kingdom	Seminary in Qum, Iran
Shaykh Azher Nasser	Iraq, United States	Hawza of Najaf
Sayed Moustafa Al-Qazwini	Iraq, United States	Seminary in Qum
Sayed Hassan Al-Qazwini (brother of Moustafa Qazwini)	Iraq, United States	Seminary in Qum
Sayed Mohammed Baqer Qazwini (son of Moustafa Qazwini)	Iraq, United States	Seminary in Qum
Syed Aqeel-ul-Gharavi	India	Seminary in Qum

¹⁰ Knowledge Production & Dissemination among Muslim diaspora in Europe (part 1, 2.iii)

¹¹ While *ulema* and scholars might be interchangeable terms, particularly considering that *aalim* translates to ‘learned/ knowledgeable’, an *aalim* is usually someone with religious training in, for instance, theology or jurisprudence, and these trainings are conducted within religious institutions. So an *aalim* is a verified expert, of sorts. A Shia scholar, however, can be someone either currently in training (with any sort of institution) or someone with a non-religious education that still gives them religious knowledge, for instance a historian or student of politics. They may transfer this expertise to Shi’ism and be regarded as knowledgeable. The categories of *aalim* and scholar can overlap.

⁹ Plural of *majlis*

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2. Public Figures and Popular Orators

This list includes Shia public figures who do not have formal training from a *hawza* seminary, but are nevertheless important in the public sphere. They may gain their expertise through other forms of learning such as self-study, experience and practice. They have different roles that contribute to different functions: *zaakireen* give *majlis* speeches, *noha-khwaan* or *sozi*¹² specialize in hymns of lament, remembrance, and joy. Some of these people write powerful poems, and all are accomplished orators. Some of these people are religious motivational speakers, fusing religious messaging with psychology and popular techniques of public speaking. They are important in the transmission of religious knowledge as they may either contradict, challenge, or supplement the knowledge being conveyed by an *aalim*. Particularly in their performance as orators, these popular public figures are highly skilled at evoking emotion and affect, and therefore they tap into the bodily register of meaning-making just as successfully as any highly-educated scholar. In offline *majalis*, many of these public speakers, especially *sozi* and *noha-khwaan*, give performances before and after the sermon, playing an important role in the experience of the *majlis*.

Public figures	Country of Origin/Residence	Medium of Expertise
Sayed Ammar Nakshawani	Iraq, United Kingdom	Public speaker, orator of <i>majalis</i>
Nadeem Sarwar	Pakistan	Noha-khwaan
Farhan Ali Waris	Pakistan	Noha-khwaan
Hashim Sisters	United Kingdom	Noha-khwaan
Syed Rehan Naqvi	Pakistan, Netherlands	Orator of <i>majalis</i> , motivational speaker

¹² *Sozi* and *Noha-khwaan* (plural: *nohay-khwaan*) both refer to people who perform religious hymns, songs, and poetry. *Noha*, in Urdu, means a song of lamentation.

It is important to note here that the exclusion of the category of ‘training’ in the table above does not indicate a lack of training; it simply indicates a gap in the ability to trace the training and expertise of such figures.

This gap reflects the narrow perspective of what is widely regarded as religious knowledge: it is clear that knowledge, even when we examine it through the instance of one ritual, does not reside in clearly sanctioned, traceable, and institutionalized domains. Let us look at the case of Ammar Nakshawani: he is a historian of Islam with a PhD. He does not hold training from a seminary, yet he has appeared on a list of ‘*The 500 Most Influential Muslims*’ in 2014¹³.

Nakshawani is wildly popular, giving *majalis* lectures in English that draw thousands of YouTube views¹⁴. Nakshawani is a voice in the Shia public sphere, sanctioned by his speeches and the output of his work online, made even more accessible through the use of English. He is a prime example of looking beyond religious seminaries as sources of knowledge production, though no doubt, a closer look would reveal that that picture is more complicated.

¹³ <https://themuslim500.com/>

¹⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCpbGS6mQ9ho3h21qjKce04Q>

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3. Organizations

Majalis are, as of yet, produced by groups of people. These groups are religious and community organizations at all levels (national, transnational, international, local), of different denominations (Twelver, Khoja), and at varying numbers of members. In the Netherlands and United Kingdom, religious organizations begin preparations for *majalis* well in advance. They book speakers, arranging for learned scholars and popular speakers to come and speak to their communities. These speeches are also broadcast online, so videos of *majalis* are hosted on the Facebook and YouTube platforms of these communities. So, these religious organizations fund *majalis*, give a stage to speakers, and provide access not just to a local audience but an online one.

Community Organization	Location	Notable Online Presence
Ahlal bait Jongeren Organisatie	Netherlands	Website: http://www.ahlal bait.nl/ Facebook, YouTube, Instagram
Ahlal bait 4 iedereen	Netherlands	Website: http://www.ahlal bait 4 iedereen.nl/ Facebook, YouTube
Stichting Al Cauther Jongeren	The Hague, Netherlands	Website: http://www.alcauther.com/ Facebook
Idara-e-Jafria Amsterdam	Netherlands	Facebook
Al-Mahdi Institute	Birmingham, United Kingdom	Website: https://www.almahdi.edu/ YouTube
MKSI Leicester	United Kingdom	Website: https://www.mksileicester.org/ YouTube, Facebook
Hyderi Islamic Center	London, United Kingdom	Website: https://www.hyderi.org.uk/ Facebook

A Note on Online Presence:

All the figures and organizations listed so far have an online presence. In fact, their digital outreach is so proliferated that a comprehensive attempt to list this would be too exhaustive. The works of these figures can be found on almost every popular social media website such as Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, and Instagram.

This work is often shared through the online presence of Shia organizations and community pages. The presence of Shia organizations, works of Shia figures, and *majlis* content are shared through WhatsApp, Telegram, and countless other messaging platforms. Alongside this, information about the biographies and works of these figures is listed on various websites of different Shia institutions and groups.

So, in online spheres, the connections between public figures and organizations mirrors the close connections occurring 'offline' as well, in the form of affiliations. At the same time, much of the presence of local and community figures is lost, as their work is either not present online or not available in organized ways that respond to digital algorithms.

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4. Actors in Digital Majalis

Digital contexts complicate the matter of ‘actors producing religious knowledge’. The next step is to ask, of course, how? ‘Actors’ is an interesting category to attempt to organize digital forms of the majalis around. As I have already established, actors that are people and groups arrange for majalis to take place and participate in the proceedings. However, when looking at digital majalis, I find these afore-mentioned categories restricting.

The production of knowledge online does not simply occur through the online presence of Shia people, including ulema, public figures and audiences. The platform also matters. This can be the platform of a group or organization that operates both offline and online (see Section 3) or a purely online community (such as a public Facebook group about Shi’ism). On the internet, knowledge can exist outside the parameters of community, even outside considerations such as intended audience (primarily Shia or other Muslims). For example, there may be a majlis video with thousands of views, uploaded by random and anonymous user. Therefore the ‘actor’ behind it could be unknown, but content has been created and engaged with nonetheless.

The reason why I call attention to this is to consider what we mean by ‘actors’ that may contest religious authority. Are actors only people? Or can materials, such as online content, also be considered actors? In this section I do not delve into the history of materiality in religion and simply take the process of digitization as my point of departure. I propose looking at digital platforms and certain forms of online content as ‘actors’, by which I mean materials that are included in the terrain of digital majalis and can reach and impact audiences, regardless of sanctioning by ulema, public figures, institutions, and organizations in the Shia public sphere. I wish to highlight the importance of medium and materiality in religious communication,

dissemination, and experience, all of which I consider part of the construction of religious knowledge. Consider, for example: materials online can spawn other content: for example, people reacting to that content- there is a whole genre now on online video platforms called Reaction Videos. This proliferation of content marks an increase in religious discussions, lectures, and debates, and contributes to a sort of democratization of knowledge that scholars have associated with certain forms of new media and the internet¹⁵.

The following is very simplistic representation of *majlis* content online, in order to look at the multiple layers of knowledge production.

Digital Platform	Majlis content	Figures contributing	Audience feedback
YouTube	Videos of majlis sermon Videos of nohay and religious hymns/songs/poetry Short informational/ motivational videos	Ulema Zaakireen Noha-khwaan and sozis Academics and intellectuals Religious bloggers	Only through comments, and even this is disabled on many videos.
Facebook	Videos of majalis Announcements of both online and offline majalis Short informational/ motivational videos Images	All of the above Community leaders/ organizational committees	Through comments, sharing and reactions; a bit easier for people to talk to each other.
WhatsApp	Announcements of both online and offline majalis Short informational/ motivational videos Images	Quite egalitarian for people to discuss and share things from any source.	

¹⁵ Heidi A. Campbell (2017) Surveying theoretical approaches within digital religion studies. *New Media and Society* 19(1): 15-24; Patrick Eisenlohr (2012) Media and Religious Diversity. *Annual Review of Anthropology* 41: 37-55.

Section 3

Transmission of Knowledge and Knowledge Production

How do ideas go, however sound, from being irreverent to tradition? While the thought (ideas, opinions, etc.) of intellectuals can be mute or marginal in one period, it can become something else, i.e., mainstream or orthodoxy, through the writings (i.e., production) of later thinkers.

My research examines the genealogy and transmission of thought in the writings of Muslim intellectuals. It not only traces ideas but seeks to understand how ideas become canon through writings and transmission. My research studies the thought and writings of Muhammad b. Ahmad al-Qurtubi (d. 1273) in his commentary on the Qur'an titled, *The Legal Ruling of the Qur'an*. Al-Qurtubi was an Andalusian from the city of Cordoba; when the city fell in 1238 to the Christians in the north, he immigrated to Alexandria. The commentary is encyclopaedic and is nearly a line-by-line interpretation of the Qur'an. His commentary had high circulation among the *ulama* soon after its completion, and it was one of the earliest encyclopedic commentaries printed in the

modern world. Moreover, the commentary brings together a vast history of religious thought and writings into the work, a history of scholarship of almost five centuries. My initial research has found that the commentary of al-Qurtubi played an important role in the transmission of knowledge. It integrated the Andalusian and North African quranic exegetical tradition into the mainstream of Sunni encyclopedic tradition. How al-Qurtubi's work achieved this is a principal question of my project.

My research will identify those Andalusian and North African sources (names, titles, etc.). It will examine the opinions and statements cited in it. It will then show the representation of each source (to what extent each is represented) in the exegesis. But this process of knowledge transmission was not achieved by one person. This study will consider the role that collegial networks and institutional forms of authority played in the transmission of ideas. Nearly every scholar in the Middle Period (945–1503),

to use Marshall Hodgson's periodization of Islamic history¹⁶, acquired knowledge and prestige by studying with recognized masters who formed part of a chain of authority of transmission (sanad) going back to the Prophet Muhammad and earned licenses (s. *ijaza*) to teach the transmitted sciences. Al-Qurtubi's training came out of these institutional forms of authority. Al-Qurtubi was part of a network of colleagues situated throughout the Islamic West and Near East through which pertinent legal matters of the day were discussed and books and manuscripts discovered and exchanged.

The role that these Islamic institutions, especially in terms of "knowledge production," played in transmitting ideas of Andalusian and North African thinkers is a question that will be examined. The third question will explore how Andalusian and North African sources become mainstream and accepted into the canon of the exegetical tradition. To answer this, a study of post-Qurtubi scholarship will be

studied. How did commentators post-Qurtubi—Abu Hayyan Athir al-Din al-Gharnati (d. 1344), Jalal al-Din al-Suyuti (d. 1505), Muhammad al-Tahir b. 'Ashur (d. 1973), to name a few—engage the commentary and cite it and draw from it in their own works?

A study of post-Qurtubi commentators would reveal how *The Legal Ruling of the Qur'an* brought the ideas of Andalusian and North African thinkers of the quranic exegetical tradition into the mainstream of Sunni encyclopedic tradition.

¹⁶ Marshall G.S. Hodgson (1974) *The Venture of Islam: Conscience and History in a World Civilization*. 3 vols., Chicago: Chicago University Press.

Section 3

Transmission of Knowledge and Knowledge Production

1. Al-Qurtubi's masters: from Córdoba to Cairo

Scholar / Master	Expertise	Works
Abu al- 'Abbas Ahmad b. 'Umar b. al-Ansari al-Qurtubi aka Ibn al-Muzayyin (d. 1258)	Theology Jurisprudence of Malik Prophetic Traditions	<i>Al-Mufhim</i> (a commentary on Sahih Muslim)
Abu Ja'far Ibn Abi Hujja (d. 1245)	The seven variant readings of the Qur'an	Unknown
Abu 'Amir Yahya b. 'Abd al-Rahman b. Ahmad b. Rabi' al-Ash'ari (d. 1242)	Jurisprudence of Malik Legal theory Prophetic Traditions	Numerous works on legal theory, disputation, and dogmatic theology

2. Al-Qurtubi's students and transmission chain of knowledge production

Scholar / Master	Expertise	Works
Abu al-Ja'far b. Zubayr (d. 1300)	Language Jurisprudence of Malik Legal theory Prophetic Traditions	<i>Al-Milak al-ta'wil</i> (a commentary on the Qur'an)
Abu al-Qasim Ibn Juzayy (d. 1340)	Language Jurisprudence of Malik Legal theory Prophetic Traditions	<i>Al-tas'hil</i> (a commentary on the Qur'an)

Section 3

Transmission of Knowledge and Knowledge Production

3. Post-Qurtubi: Commentators that engage with al-Qurtubi's commentary

Exegete / Commentator	Expertise	Exegesis/Commentary
Jalal al-Din al-Suyuti (d. 1505)	Language Exegesis Jurisprudence Legal theory Prophetic Traditions	<i>Al-Milak al-ta'wil</i> (a commentary on the Qur'an)
Muhammad al-Shawkani (d. 1839)	Language Jurisprudence Legal theory Prophetic Traditions	<i>Fath al-Qadir</i>
Sayyid Qutb (d. 1966)	Politics Modernity Exegesis	<i>Fi zilal al-Qur'an</i>
Ibn 'Ashur (d. 1973)	Language Jurisprudence of Malik Legal theory Prophetic Traditions	<i>Tafhim al-Qur'an</i>